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IMPACT OF CLIMATIC VARIATION ON GROUNDWATER - A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Worldwide climatic parameter characteristics are influenced due to Climatic variations. Investigations have been carried out by climatologists in order to find a possible relation of climate change with anthropogenic behavior by studying trends in different climatic parameters. However, the changes are not in same pattern for all the regions especially in India due to localized intensity and must be quantified locally to manage the natural resources. Temperature and Precipitation are the most important components of climatic parameter, has been widely measured as a starting point towards the apprehension of climate changes courses. Aim of the study is to find the trend in maximum temperature, minimum temperature and precipitation using non-parametric methods (i.e. the Mann–Kendall and Sen’s T tests) in the district of Saharanpur. It is facing adverse effects of less rainfall almost every year, with a notable change in the pre monsoon and post-monsoon temperatures. This is an effort to analyse one of the most important climatic variable i.e. average temperature, for analyzing the temperature trend in the area. Monthly data of 110 years from 1907 to 2016 has been processed in the study in order to find out the monthly variability of average temperature and precipitation for which Mann-Kendall (MK) Test has been used together with the Sen’s Slope Estimator for the determination of trend and slope magnitude. Monthly average temperature trend has been identified here to achieve the objective which has been shown with 110 years of data. There are rising rates of average temperature in some months and decreasing trend in some other months, The magnitudes of trend in precipitation is also obtained by these statistical tests suggesting overall significant changes in the area.

Keywords: Air temperature, non-parametric tests, trend analysis, auto correlation, MK and Sen’s tests.

Introduction:

Climate change, also called global warming, refers to the rise in average surface temperatures on Earth. An overwhelming scientific consensus maintains that climate change is due primarily to the human use of fossil fuels, which releases carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the air. The gases trap heat within the atmosphere, which can have a range of effects on ecosystems, including rising sea levels, severe weather events, and droughts that render landscapes more susceptible to wildfires.

The primary cause of climate change is the burning of fossil fuels, such as oil and coal, which emits greenhouse gases into the atmosphere—primarily carbon dioxide. Other human activities, such as agriculture and deforestation, also contribute to the proliferation of greenhouse gases that cause climate change.

Although climate change occurs naturally, the increase in human population and deforestation for land use (e.g. urbanization) have substantially accelerated the increase of greenhouse gases. The increase in urban, industrial and agricultural water demand will further increase pressure on water resources. As we know surface water is limited in the arid and semi-arid regions, groundwater plays a dominant role in water supply in this area. However, quantification of water components, especially groundwater recharge, is therefore essential for using and managing water resources efficiently. Further, increase in climate and land use can significantly affect water resources and hydrological cycle.

Air temperature and precipitation are key elements of weather systems, therefore the examination of their behavior is important for understanding of climate variability because both are highly variable spatially and temporarily at different local, regional and global scales (Karabulut et. al, 2008). According to the report of Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2007) the seasonal, annual and spatial variation in precipitation trends were observed during past decades in all over Asia.

Scientific results ensured that due to increased concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, the climate change of Earth begun to manifest itself; temperature is increasing due to which the amount and distribution of rainfall is being altered (Yue and Hashino, 2003; Andrighetti et al., 2009). The IPCC Scientific Assessment suggests that global average temperature may increase between 1.5 °C and 4.5°C, with a ‘best estimate’ of 2.0°C, in the next century with a twice of the CO² concentration in the atmosphere. Global warming induced changes in temperature and rainfall are already evident in many parts of the world.

Kothawale and Rupa Kumar 2005 found that precipitation trends increases can result in an increase in the floods frequency and a decrement could lead to drought. An increasing trend of temperature leads to more evaporation, which in turn, increases precipitation. It is found that over 1901–2003, mean annual temperature of all India has risen at the rate of 0.05 °C/decade, which is mostly due to the rise of maximum temperature (0.07 °C/decade) and minimum temperature (0.02 °C/decade).

Increasing trend in precipitation due to climatic variation was predicted in the upper Ganga canal command area which is contributing to the prolonged and heavy rainfall that is rising with time. Climate is often defined loosely as the average weather at a particular place, incorporating such features as temperature, precipitation, humidity, and windiness. A more specific definition would state that climate is the mean state and variability of these features over some extended time period. Both definitions acknowledge that the weather is always changing, owing to

instabilities in the atmosphere. And as weather varies from day to day, so too does climate vary, from daily day-and-night cycles up to periods of geologic time hundreds of millions of years long. In a very real sense, climate variation is a redundant expression—climate is always varying. No two years are exactly alike, nor are any two decades, any two centuries, or any two millennia.

Literature Review:

The vast variation in climate has disrupted major climatic parameters globally. Concurrence of scientific evidence shows that climate change has begun to manifest itself, globally, in the form of increased downpours and storms, rising temperature and sea level, retreating glaciers, etc.

Climate change refers to any significant change in a climate variable (e.g. temperature, precipitation, or wind) for a decade or longer (IPCC, 2001). It might interrupt from natural factors or human activities. The term “global warming” is often used interchangeably with the term “climate change”. Global warming refers to the increasing average temperature which can contribute to global climate pattern variation. However, increasing temperatures are just one aspect of climate change.

Human activities are adding to the concentration of greenhouse gases. The carbon dioxide (CO₂) level has increased since the 1950s. Climate change due to temperature increases can have negative effects on the hydrological cycle through precipitation, evapotranspiration, and soil moisture. According to IPCC, reports that the global mean surface temperature has raised 0.6 ± 0.2 °C since 1861, and estimates an increase of 2 to 4 °C over the next 100 years (Singh & Kumar, 2010).

Worldwide climatologists are putting forward their data to find possible relation of climate difference with anthropogenic behavior by studying trends in different climatic parameter .Specially , in India climate change in some region are not equal due to localized intensity .Aim of this study is to determine trend in annual mean and monthly temperature as well as the temporal variability of rainfall for a century (1901-2010) (110 yrs).The magnitude of trend in a temperature and annual precipitation using Mann –Kendall and Sen ‘s test. Auto correlation effect is reduced from the temperature series and annual before precipitation applying Mann –Kendall test. In present study, the investigation shows the spartial and temporal variability in the mean, minimum and maximum precipitation and temperature of upper Ganga canal command localist in Uttarakhand. The annual mean, maximum and minimum temperature has increased by 0.60° C, 0.60° C and 0.62° C respectively over the past 101 years (Khare 2013).

Climatic variability can be described as the annual difference in values of specific climatic variables within averaging periods such as a 30 year period (Karabulut et al, 2008). The climatologists agree that there has been a large-scale warming of the Earth’s surface over the last one hundred years or so. The globe is warming due to anthropogenic factors such as emission of greenhouse gases. The climate is changing due to global warming in the

Hindukush-Karakoram-Himalaya (HKH) region. The warming in the higher Himalaya of HKH is greater than the global average temperature (Parker and Horton, 1999; IPCC, 2001; Jones and Moberg, 2003).

In recent years, remote sensing has played a positive role in environmental monitoring such as for ecosystem variations and land degradation, especially in dry lands. Climate variations can significantly affect ecosystem variations and land degradation. Additionally, there are anthropogenic factors, ecosystem disparities and land degradation affected by climate variations such as drought and desiccation (Lambin & Ehrlich, 1996), oscillation of rainfall (Anymba et al., 2001; Olsson et al., 2006) and rising of temperature (Xiao & Moody, 2004).

Analysis of Mann-Kendall test shows annually increasing non significance trend in rainfall time series in Garhwal region district of U.K. These areas are under the experience of heavy rainfall for short duration. This ultimately leads to more runoff in these areas and very less scope of groundwater recharge. Thus, these data give a broad overview of the regional precipitation and temperature behavior in study region (Mishra et.al. 2014).

Temperature and annual rainfall are main components of climate and changes in their pattern can affect human health, ecosystems, plants, animals and water bodies. With increase in temperature heat wave are generated and can have devastating effects like illness and death in susceptible populations. In addition, temperature changes can cause a change in number of animal and plant species. Similar variation in rainfall pattern and its timing can have widespread effect on the availability of water and force animal and plant species in their migration. Increases in precipitation trends can also result in an increase in the frequency of floods and could thereby impact water quality. On the other hand, a decrease in precipitation trend could imply an increase in instances of drought. (Kothawale and Rupa Kumar, 2005). The study on temperature in the high altitude regions of Uttarakhand found an increasing trend in average temperature in the region. The main objective of this study is to identify the monotonic trend of precipitation and temperature rise by using MK Test and Sen's Slop estimator. (Kripalani et al. 2014).

The two variables, temperature and precipitation, are directly proportional to each other. An increase in Earth's temperature leads to more evaporation and cloud formation to occur, which in turn, increases precipitation. The mean annual temperature in India is rising at the rate of 0.05 °C/decade over 1901–2003 which is mostly due to the rise of maximum temperature (0.07 °C/decade) rather than because of the rise of minimum temperature (0.02 °C/decade) (Kothawale and Rupa Kumar, 2005).

There will be fall of -0.38°C per century in the north Indian average temperature with a contrasting rise of 0.42°C per century depicted by average temperature of India during the last half of 20th century (Arora et.al. 2005). The seasonal and annual air temperatures from 1881–1997 were analyzed that has shown an increase in trend of mean annual temperature, at the rate of 0.57C per 100 years (Pant & Kumar 1997). With the help of tree rings to rebuild the pre-monsoon temperature records in the western Himalayas and observed the decreasing trend during the second half of the 20th century (Yadav et al. 2004).

Upper Ganga Canal Command area with level of non-significant trend. Increasing trend in rainfall was predicted in the Upper Ganga Canal Command Area and it was concluded that there may be an impact of climate change which is adding to the prolonged and heavy rainfall that is rising with time. (Mishra et al., 2013) The effects of climatic change and variability have been analyzed by several researchers in the past half-century, because of higher demographic pressure, contributing to climatic changes and variability. The problem is more severe in India and China where population is huge and poses continuous threat to the fresh water. Gleick, (2000), reported that these

two countries have utilized about 40% of global freshwater for the purpose of irrigation. (Gleick, 1993, 2000; Vorosmarty et al., 2000; Shiklomanov and Rodda, 2003; Milliman et al., 2008).

Researcher has provided detailed analysis of massive rainfall events during Indian monsoon period with increase (decrease) in the frequency and magnitude of extreme (moderate) rain events over central India (Goswami et al. 2006). In India the increasing trend is found in the annual mean temperature, annual Maximum temperature and annual minimum temperature. Few research studies have been conducted separately on various cities in India and found the mixed trends in temperature series. In regional parts, it has been shown diurnal asymmetry of temperature trends, indicating that the warming over India was solely contributed by maximum temperature. It was emphasized on the temporal and spatial changes in temperature over several regions of India.

The Report of Fourth Assessment of the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change shows that the global mean surface air temperature increased by 0.74°C while the global mean sea surface temperature (SST) rose by 0.67°C over the last century. Analysis of global observed changes in daily climate extremes of temperature and precipitation shows widespread significant changes in temperature extremes associated with warming. Over the mountainous regions, such as the Swiss (Polish Alps, the Rockies and Andes).studies have indicated significant increase in the surface air temperatures. In the Himalayan mountain ranges, a limited number of studies in Nepal, covering some parts of the Himalayas and Tibet have also revealed similar trends based on earlier publications. It was illustrated pre-monsoon temperature cooling over the WH during the latter part of the 20th century. It was founded that the time series of temperature for the period 1851–1975 over Nepal was characterized by decadal variations but no long-term trends. Also, it was noted that the spring snow cover area has been declining and snow has been melting faster from winter to spring after mid 1990s over the western Himalayas region based on satellite derived data for the period 1986–2000 (Khare et.al. 2014).

Seasonal flow forecasting with respect to the climate change would be an efficient tool for the management of water resources for national power management, by providing an early indication of surplus or shortfall in hydropower, further it will be helpful for planners (Fowler and Archer, 2005).

Traditionally, climate patterns have been investigated using trend analysis on a point-by-point basis. Temperature and precipitation trends from one location have been compared with surrounding locations. This is appropriate when large distances separate monitoring locations. However, advanced spatial analysis is possible when monitoring locations are clustered in a local region. The use of regional average, in general, provides a time series that is a better representation of large-scale climatic processes, and it is easier to deal with one index series that is a spatially averaged series in a region. This study focuses on trend detection in annual and seasonal maximum, minimum, mean and diurnal temperature for the Mangla catchment and its sub-catchments. The study was conducted to assess the effect of climate change at spatio-temporal scale for Mangla catchment and its four sub catchments (Kunhar, Neelum, Kanshi and Poonch) on a regional data for the period (1971-2010) (Chaudhry and Sheikh, 2002; Chaudhry and Rasul, 2007; Afzal et al., 2009).

Conclusion:

The development and management of groundwater are complex issues for which a realistic assessment of the utilizable groundwater potential available for various uses is very important. With the increase in urbanization the area for the recharge of the groundwater is also decreasing for which the study is very important. So the impact of the climatic change will affect the study area and will cause a change in its status.

The impact of urbanization on groundwater has a major concern over past few decades, and in particular, for those involved in ground- water quantity and qualitative studies. Increment in impervious area due to urbanization results in decreased infiltration, and finally affecting the groundwater storage.

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